

- High absorbent concentration (DEA – 4 mol/L) and high acid gas loading (1 mol of acid gas per 1 mol of DEA) for highly efficient and complete acid gas removal.
- **MDEA:**
 - Aqueous solution of pure MDEA for selective H₂S removal or H₂S enrichment.
- **Activated MDEA:**
 - Used in all processes for complete acid gas removal and bulk CO₂ removal; the solution contains patented activators.

This technology offers advantages such as partial or complete regeneration of the solvent through pressure letdown during CO₂ removal. Various process configurations are available for all these treatments, ranging from conventional schemes with absorption and thermal regeneration to more advanced designs. For example, the dual split-flow configuration shown in **Figure 2** allows for maximum purification efficiency and minimized energy consumption.

Figure 2. AdvAmine Process Flowchart

The configurations of gas treating units using aqueous alkanolamine solutions primarily differ in the method of absorbent introduction. Four main methods can be identified:

Method 1 – The absorbent solution is introduced as a single stream to the top tray of the absorber at a temperature of 30–40°C. This method is typically used when the hydrogen sulfide and carbon dioxide content in the gas is relatively low, and, consequently, the total heat effect of the reactions is minimal.

Figure 3. Single-stream gas treating scheme using ethanolamine solutions
legend:

- I – Feed gas, II – treated gas, III – expander gas, IV – acid gas, V – steam**
1 – absorber, 2, 9 – pumps, 3, 7 – coolers, 4 – Expander, 5 – Heat exchanger, 6 – desorber (stripper), 8 – Separator, 10 – Reboiler, 11 – Regenerated amine storage tank

Method 2 – Introduction of the absorbent in two streams at the same temperature (30–40°C).

This method is suitable for raw gas with high concentrations of acid components. A portion of the regenerated amine stream (65–75% by mass) is fed to an intermediate tray in the middle section of the absorber. As it flows downward over the trays, the amine contacts the upward gas stream, which is introduced below the bottom tray of the absorber. In the lower section of the column, intensive interaction occurs between the acid gases and the amine, leading to a temperature increase due to the exothermic nature of the reactions. As the temperature rises, the chemical equilibrium of the target reactions shifts in the reverse direction, reducing the acid gas removal efficiency. The excess heat is removed from the column with the saturated absorbent stream.

In the upper part of the absorber, the gas stream comes into contact with fresh, cooled absorbent fed to the top tray, allowing for additional removal of acid components from the gas. This amine introduction method reduces power consumption for pumping and decreases absorbent usage while still achieving the required level of gas purification.

Figure 4. Scheme of amine solution feed with equal (A) and different (B) absorbent temperatures

Legend:

1 – Feed gas, 2 – Treated gas, 3 – Saturated absorbent solution, 4 – Regenerated absorbent solution, 1 – Absorber, 2 – Cooler

Method 3 – Introduction of the absorbent in two streams at different temperatures. In this case, 70–75% of the amine solution is fed into the middle of the absorber at a temperature of 60–70°C, while the remainder is fed to the top tray of the absorber at 30–40°C. This method is applied when the raw gas contains COS and CS₂. Creating a high-temperature zone in the lower part of the absorber increases the extraction of acid components due to the hydrolysis reactions of COS and CS₂:

The formed hydrogen sulfide and carbon dioxide then react with the amine in the upper zone of the absorption column.

Method 4 – Introduction of the amine solution in two streams with different degrees of regeneration. This method is used for treating gases with high acid gas content. The amine feed scheme differs from the previous one in that a partially regenerated solution is fed into the middle section of the absorber; this solution is taken from one of the trays of the desorber and cooled in a heat exchanger to 50–60°C. Only part of the solution undergoes deep regeneration and is fed to the top of the absorber at 40–50°C to ensure fine purification of the gas. This scheme is more

economical than the traditional one by 10–15% due to reduced steam consumption during regeneration.

Thus, we select **Method 3**, which involves feeding the amine solution in two streams with different temperatures, as this method increases the extraction efficiency of acid components.

The formation of degradation products in alkanolamine solutions is one of the major issues encountered during gas treating unit operation. This leads to operational disturbances, deterioration of treated gas quality, absorbent losses, and consequently, the need to reduce gas processing capacity.

The main cause of degradation products is impurities entering the absorbent with the raw gas (liquid hydrocarbons, formation water, mechanical impurities, corrosion inhibitors, surfactants, resins, etc.). Other significant factors include high process temperatures, pressure fluctuations, lubricating oils, corrosion products, and amine foaming.

To prevent these problems, the gas processing plant implements the following key measures:

1. Minimizing impurities in the feed gas that cause or promote foaming, corrosion, and formation of by-products.
2. Periodic washing and cleaning of equipment from sludge.
3. Filtration of the circulating amine solution through activated carbon (AC) layers to remove substances causing excessive foaming. Between 5 and 20% of the circulating absorbent solution passes through the filtration system.
4. Use of antifoaming agents and corrosion inhibitors [22].

However, all these measures have drawbacks:

1. The use of defoamers does not completely eliminate the foam-causing agents but only temporarily suppresses foaming. Overdosing defoamers results in the formation of more stable and difficult-to-extinguish foam.
2. Activated carbon filtration is effective only for a limited period. During carbon replacement, the amine filtration unit is completely shut down, causing accumulation of foaming substances [8, 25].

Furthermore, filtering the entire amine volume through carbon filters requires increasing the number of filters and the volume of spent adsorbent, resulting in a sharp rise in maintenance costs. According to the existing scheme, a series of coarse and fine filters are installed on the regenerated amine feed line to capture activated carbon carried with the amine solution.

Operating under this scheme involves operations such as weekly replacement of the filter medium in FL01 (cellulose), monthly steaming of carbon filters (vented to atmosphere), washing of filters, and quarterly replacement of the entire volume of activated carbon in the filtration unit.

The adsorbent replacement process is lengthy and labor-intensive. Before replacing the carbon, the filter and the entire filtration system are steamed out and vented to the atmosphere. After steaming and cooling the filter, it is opened and the carbon is manually unloaded, which requires significant labor effort.

The activated carbon is also loaded manually through the top hatch of the unit. After loading, the carbon filter is filled with water, drained, and put into operation. Based on the above, alternative methods for removing foaming agents from the alkanolamine absorbent solution, free from the listed drawbacks, have been proposed. The most promising is the extraction process, where the removal of foaming agents is carried out by extraction [24].

Figure 5. Process flow diagram of the existing amine solution adsorption filtration unit:

T01 – Amine storage tank, FL01 – coarse filter, FL02 A, B – Carbon filters

FL03 A, B – Filters for removing entrained activated carbon from amine solution

FL04 – fluoroplastic filter, P01 – amine pump

1 – Amine solution for filtration

2 – Amine solution to absorption stage

3 – Filtered amine solution to storage tank

Polyphenyl ethers (PPE) grades 5F4E and N-PPE are proposed as extractants. The effectiveness of PPE as an extractant for removing foaming substances from the amine absorbent solution has been proven by laboratory studies. All of the above will lead to a significant improvement in the technical and economic performance of the amine gas treating unit at the gas processing plant (GPP). Furthermore, the disposal of spent materials (activated carbon at 29 tons per year, etc.), as well as the elimination of steaming and washing of carbon filters and other filtration elements from the operating cycle, will reduce harmful emissions into the atmosphere. Therefore, the modernized process will substantially improve the environmental situation in Uzbekistan at the plant's location.

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